

ARTICLE TYPE: Original Article

HARMONIZING IDENTITY: FEMINIST PERSPECTIVES ON MUSICAL EXPRESSION IN BARBARA PROBST’S *THE SOUND BETWEEN THE NOTES*

Shruthi K^{1*} and Dr. S. Gomathi²

^{1*}Research Scholar, Department of English, PSGR Krishnammal College for Women, Coimbatore, India.

²Assistant Professor, Department of English, PSGR Krishnammal College for Women, Coimbatore, India

ARTICLE INFO	ABSTRACT
Received: 05/07/2025 Accepted: 28/07/2025	<p>The paper explores the relationship between feminist aesthetics and musical expression, specifically from the perspectives of identity and representation of women. The primary objective of the study is achieved by applying “Feminist Aesthetics” by Carolyn Korsmeyer and Peg Brand Weiser. The theory introduces social construction of identity, and how each of these aspects is shaped by elements like race, national origin, socioeconomic status, and historical context, are reflected and perpetuated by feminist viewpoints in aesthetics. Throughout history, women have been actively involved in music, especially in literature where their experiences and contributions are frequently discussed. Piano became associated with modesty and femininity. Numerous female writers have won significant awards for their musical novels. <i>The Sound Between the Notes</i> by Barbara Probst is one such novel. It examines the complications of identity, especially for women juggling personal aspirations with household responsibilities, it is incredibly pertinent to today's society. Drawing from the novel <i>The Sound Between the Notes</i> by Barbara Probst, this paper offers insights into the challenges and opportunities for women in the field of music. The analysis spans a variety of contexts, including character analysis, narrative technique, thematic study and music as a metaphorical element. The paper concludes with the scope for further research. Key findings suggest that <i>The Sound Between the Notes</i> is an effective reminder of how important it is to follow one's passions while managing relationships and life's obstacles to create one’s identity.</p>
Keywords Music, Feminism, Aesthetics, Barbara Probst, Identity, representation	
Corresponding Author Name: Shruthi K Email: shruthi.k.guhapriya@gmail.com	

INTRODUCTION

According to Victor Hugo, "Music expresses that which cannot be said and on which it is impossible to be silent" (Probst, 2021, p. 195). Throughout history, women have been actively involved in music, especially in literature where their experiences and contributions are frequently discussed. The dual character of women's musical roles was frequently represented in this era's literature, including conduct books and novels. They were maintaining social norms and likewise providing women a way to push back against them. Writings by authors like Jane Austen alongside other lady's journals emphasized the role that music had in courting and social dynamics, showing how women used music to negotiate their identities. Numerous female writers have written noteworthy musical novels such as, Alice Walker's *The Colour Purple* (1982) won Pulitzer Prize for Fiction in 1983 and National Book Award, Ann Patchett won the Women's Prize for Fiction in 2002 for *Bel Canto* (2001) and Chimamanda Ngozi Adichie's *Half of a Yellow Sun* (2006) won the Women's Prize in 2007. In general, women's musical experiences and societal roles have been explored and honoured through literature.

Research Objectives

This study investigates the relationship between feminist philosophy and musical expression, specifically from the perspectives of identity and community involvement. It also emphasizes the ways in which these components can both reflect and defy gender and identity norms in society. It is done by applying the "Feminist Aesthetics" theory of Carolyn Korsmeyer and Peg Brand Weiser.

Significance of the Study

Music played a significant role in women's life, primarily among the middle class during the nineteenth century. Especially, piano became associated with modesty and femininity, giving women a means of expressing themselves within the boundaries of domesticity. A confluence of social, cultural, and economic circumstances led to piano's close relationship with women in the 19th century. Piano is a major motif in a number of literary works, which highlights its importance in the nineteenth century's society and culture, including *The Piano* (1913) by D.H. Lawrence, *Pride and Prejudice* (1813) by Jane Austen, *Jane Eyre* (1847) by Charlotte Bronte, *Madame Bovary* (1856) by Gustave Flaubert, *Vanity Fair* (1848) by William Thackeray, and *The Sound Between the Notes* (2021) by Barbara Probst. This paper tries to analyse the representation of women through music as explicated in *The Sound Between the Notes* by Barbara Probst.

***The Sound Between the Notes* by Barbara Probst**

Barbara Probst was a renowned American author, who received the Association of European Journalists' twenty fifth Francisco Cerecedo Prize and Women Together Award in 2007. She worked as

a faculty in Sarah Lawrence College. She is also known for her essays published in various journals. *The Beat of Life, Arriving Where We, Equine-Trading and Ecstasy* and *Smart Hearts in the City* were some of the works written by Probst. She has drawn appreciation from critics for her ability to elicit a wide range of emotions, from joy to dread, which helps to make the story psychological and real. Her novel, *The Sound Between the Notes*' influence was strengthened when it was selected as one of Kirkus Reviews' Best Indie Books of 2021, highlighting its continued influence in modern literature.

The Sound Between the Notes is divided into seven parts. Novel opens with the audition and the way Susannah finds out that she is affected by Dupuytren's contracture. Though Susannah gets to relaunch her career after sixteen years, her medical condition tries to fail her in the big concert. But when she shares about her disease with her husband, he promises to support her. Her son James, who is in his teenage years, has a careless attitude towards the happenings in the home. Part two talks about Susannah's adoption by Tyler and Dana and when she tries to trace her birth parents, she utterly fails in the mission. Part three focuses on Susannah's preparations for the concert and how there is a misunderstanding between her husband Aaron and Susanna, which leads to indecisiveness on the radiation treatment. Also in this part, Susannah learns about the death of her birth mother eventually leading to the discovery of a sister named Simone who is also associated with music. Part five recollects her encounter with her birth father and her sister Simone. It almost functions as a turning point of the novel, as Susannah decides to go ahead with the radiation treatment in order to perform well in the concert. In the due course, she overcomes various personal dilemmas that stops her from professional accomplishments. For once Susannah decides to put behind everything that has been holding her and goes ahead with her dream of becoming world's renowned pianist. Part six narrates the incidents on concert day. And the final part is about the reconciliation of Susannah with her family, where both her husband and son support her, to place her music before the family's needs.

LITERATURE REVIEW

The goal of the research paper titled "After Relational Aesthetics: Improvised Musics, the social, and (re)theorising the Aesthetic" (2016), is to demonstrate the presence of art and aesthetics and the unique forms that should not be ignored, where Georgina Born states that:

My aim has been twofold: to show that while the social is increasingly manifest in contemporary art and aesthetics, and theorised as such, it takes distinctive forms, which matter and should not be conceptually elided; and on this basis, to enable fertile comparisons to be drawn between the varieties of social aesthetics in contemporary art practices and those evident in improvised musics. (Born, 2016, p. 5)

The Emergence, Circulation, And Influence of Turn-Of-Millennium Feminist Music for Girl Audiences in The United States (2024) by Orita, states that the massive changes in sociopolitics were

sparked by musical manifestations of girlhood, "Turn-of-millennium musical expressions of girlhood precipitated massive shifts in US socio-politics that transformed public perceptions - and girls' self-perceptions - of girls feminist political identity and influence" (Orita, 2024, p. 3).

In the research paper "Toward a Feminist Critical Perspective in Music History" (1993) by Molly Weaver, it is stated how feminist perspective is viewed as progressive instead of mainstream, "The reality that feminists play a small role creatively and critically in music. In the academy, high regard for the validity of the feminist view is still considered "progressive" rather than "mainstream" (p.35).

These papers focus on aesthetics and music is only a small concept of their broader enquiry. The limitations of the prior studies is the lack of focus on women in music and absence of representation of feminist viewpoints in aesthetics.

METHODS

Qualitative Methodology involving non-numerical data such as textual analysis to explore concepts, experiences and social phenomena is used. Methodology discussed in Seventh Edition of American Psychological Association (APA-7) is followed.

RESULTS

Though Susannah Lewis is a talented classical pianist, she chose a sixteen-year hiatus from performing. When she is given the chance to perform again as her son gets nearer to adulthood, her love for music rekindles. She overcomes some obstacles such as becoming aware that she has Dupuytren's contracture, a genetic disorder that affects her fingers and jeopardizes her career as a professional pianist. The account of health and vulnerability highlights Susannah's battle with Dupuytren's contracture that becomes a hinderance to her skill to perform on the piano. Her emotional battle and self-discovery are vivid in a metaphorical portrayal through music in *The Sound Between the Notes*. The emotional obstacles she must overcome in order to rediscover her love of music are symbolized by her physical frailty. Susannah faces both personal and professional challenges with resilience, which finally leads to discovering oneself and musical enlightenment. Any individual who has ever felt caught between duty and ambition may relate to Susannah's struggle to regain her musical career after years of selflessness as it speaks to the human yearning for fulfilment and acknowledgment.

DISCUSSIONS

Leading stalwarts in the field of feminist aesthetics, Carolyn Korsmeyer and Peg Brand Weiser made an important contribution with their edited anthology, *Feminism and Tradition in Aesthetics*. This collection investigates the relationship between feminist theory and conventional philosophical aesthetics. As a Research Professor of Philosophy, Korsmeyer has written a number of important books.

Brand Weiser is employed by the University of Arizona as an adjunct instructor. Their joint work highlights the necessity of reevaluating aesthetic standards from a feminist perspective.

According to early theoreticians, philosophy is known for its supposedly neutral and inclusive language, but gender is present in almost every area of the discipline's fundamental conceptual frameworks. Therefore, "Feminist Aesthetics" explores the ways in which conceptions of art, artists, and aesthetics' worth are shaped by gender. The theory introduces social construction of identity, and how each of these aspects is shaped by elements like race, national origin, socioeconomic status, and historical context, are reflected and perpetuated by feminist viewpoints in aesthetics. The purpose of concert for the protagonist changes as the novel progresses, though it started for her loved ones, later it was for herself. This aspect is seen in the novel in the following lines, "At first, the concert had been for Vera, to earn back her respect... The concert wasn't for Vera anymore. It wasn't even for Aaron. It was for herself, Susannah. For the self she was meant to be" (Probst, 2021, p. 264).

Secondly, "Mimetic" nature or the imitative techniques are the ones that most closely match our contemporary conception of art, for example, music mimics voices, the sounds present in the nature including symbolic representation of human emotions. Ingleton in his research paper titled "Feminist Process in Sound Arts and Experimental Musics" (2014), reflected the same idea stating that, "Woman has been historically silenced, erased, ignored and disqualified from and misrepresented within dominant historical sound and music histories" (Ingleton, 2014, p. 15). This shows how women have been misrepresented throughout the history by the means of suppression, elimination and neglect. In the novel, Susannah too, mimics Schubert's sonata in the concert, who she remembers was in agony, and channelised all of his need into music. She needed the same dedication and emotion. It is expressed in the following words, "Then she thought of Schubert, dying at thirty-one, ugly, isolated, in pain, pouring all of his yearning and ecstasy into the music. No one had the right to play his sonata without the same commitment, the same passion" (Probst, 2021, p. 6).

The third core idea, according to Korsmeyer is that universality offers a broader perspective than specificity, universality is thought to be preferable. For instance, since reason is thought to be a more trustworthy ability than emotion, it is more effective. These choices show a bias in favour of "objectivity" over "subjectivity," two ideas with particularly nuanced meanings in the field of aesthetics. Epstein remarked in *A Feminist Theology of Music* as, "illicit musical practices with the rhetoric of effeminacy, thus veiling male ambivalence toward women and the body in a politics of transcendence" (Epstein, 2000, p.5). According to him, there is a transcendence while combining the illicit music with effeminate discourse. The protagonist too felt she had nothing to give if her music wasn't able to carry him away. This concept leads to a problem between Susannah and Aaron:

Knowing and advising were the ways Aaron showed his love. If he couldn't do that, he had nothing to give her... It was the same way she felt about her music. If she couldn't transport him with her playing, she had nothing to offer. (Probst, 2021, p. 263)

Theoreticians also state that the ability to perform music for family and friends at home was seen as a social possession for young girls who were raised well by the family. Schiller reflects in *Resilience & Melancholy: Pop Music, Feminism, Neoliberalism* as, "So, when resilience is the dominant norm of neoliberalism, and if contemporary pop music often performs acts of resilience, does this imply the impossibility of alternative strategies of survival that do not feed into the oppressing structures causing them?" (Schiller, 2017, p.5). It is clear that resilience is frequently performed in the acts of music. This ideology prevailed in the novel too. The protagonist values her caregiver more than her birth mother. It is seen in the following lines:

It struck her, suddenly, that neither of them had really had Corinne for a mother, not if mother meant someone who was there to love you and teach you and watch you grow. Simone had Pamela, who sang with her in the church choir. And she had Dana, who drove her to Boston for Piano lessons with Vera. (Probst, 2021, p. 186)

Conventionally speaking, the fifth key area of theory is that women are viewed as more emotional and sensitive but less intellectual. The realm of aesthetics has been more receptive to the beneficial applications to which emotionality and sensitivity might be put, since theory of creativity suggests that these qualities can be inspirational. This emotional benefit of music is stated in *Just a Girl? Rock Music, Feminism, and the Cultural Construction of Female Youth* (1998) by Wald as, "I believe that youth music cultures continue to offer girls important sources of emotional sanctuary and vital outlets for the expression of rage and pleasure, frustration and hope" (Wald, 1998, p. 25). So, music provides females with essential social safe spaces. Susannah experienced the agony of everything she had given up in one extremely overwhelming moment. It is expressed as:

In a single fierce instant, Susannah felt the pain of what she had lost. And with the pain, came a swell of longing. That longing had brought her all the way to the cracked stone steps of the music school where the auditions were being held. (Probst, 2021, p. 7)

The theorists have stated, "The act of giving birth was perceived as a result of women's *natural* biological role, which was seen as an expression of the gifts that nature had given them" (Korsmeyer and Weiser, 2021). McClary in "Towards A Feminist Criticism of Music" opines that, it has long been believed that music, as abstract processes of production, is immune to interpretations including those related to gender, sexuality, race, ethnicity, and class. When James was born, it was automatically considered as Susannah's role to give up her career and look after James. No one including Susannah, thought about asking her husband to help her in raising the kid together, so that her career will not be affected too. This is a driving factor of society is expressed as follows, "Newborn James had been the

reason for halting her career. Nearly sixteen years later, teenage James was the reason for resuming it, or hoping to” (Probst, 2021, p. 22).

According to Korsmeyer, the seventh concept of “Feminist Aesthetics” is the identification of a gap at the core of creative representation that leads to the questioning of history that encourages “writing the feminine” (Korsmeyer and Weiser, 2021). The theoreticians Korsmeyer and Weiser also include the counterpoint of Ewa Plonowska Ziarek stating that “worlds of art have also provided a wealth of resources to uncover realities of gender, sexuality, social position, and race” (Korsmeyer and Weiser, 2021). At the beginning Susannah was excited thinking only about things that will happen if everything goes right. Only in the later part of the novel, she ponders about what could go wrong. This duality did hit Susannah, in the following way:

And then it hit her, the truth she had missed about the concert. She had assumed that she understood the stakes: a new beginning as a musician, or back to life-as-it-was. Behind that was a second assumption: that life-as-it-was would be waiting for her in a kind of suspended animation, in case the concert led nowhere. (Probst, 2021, p. 259)

In addition to providing countless examples of subverting conventional concepts of fine art, feminist art also has additional levels of significance that set it apart from previous revolutionary movements. This concept is emphasized by Mayhew in “Women in Popular Music and the Construction of Authenticity” (1999) as, “the conservative traditional values represented by the music media concerning women's participation in popular music are negotiated by fans and fan communities” (Mayhew, 1999, p. 1). And the distinction can be clarified only by the listener, thus Susannah is dependent on Aaron to develop her musical skill. It is expressed in the following lines of the novel, “Besides, it was impossible to explain the difference in sensation to someone who wasn't a musician. Aaron wasn't particularly interested in music – except hers. That was what had drawn him to her when they met” (Probst, 2021, p. 14).

Also, the theoreticians Korsmeyer and Weiser includes the opinion of the critic Smith where he states that, “A number of artists today are using food that can be eaten, inviting the public into a participatory relationship with their works” (Korsmeyer and Weiser, 2021). Feminist Aesthetics theory states that the way that female artists use attraction is especially important because of the historic link that women have with their physical appearances. Even in the novel, importance is given to the protagonist's dress rather than the musical quality of a piano. It can be viewed in the following lines, “Much better. The piano they had in here was unbelievably ugly, hardly photogenic at all. This one is much more attractive, don't you think? Get a nice dress, you know, long and black. People like that” (Probst, 2021, p. 114).

Finally, the theory concludes by stating that as a result, feminist writings more often take into account various forms of identity in addition to women as the exclusive subject. Furthermore, feminists have improved them and above all, developed independent theories. Therefore, women have been at the

forefront of self-referential examinations of identity and independence, frequently through performance art. Identity and belonging are two major issues that are explored in *The Sound Between the Notes*. Susannah, the main character, struggles with her identity as an adopted person and her attempt to discover her ancestry. The narrative explores the intricacies of kinship and the yearning for acceptance, especially as they pertain to the protagonist's professional and personal lives. Susannah's earlier experiences as an adoptee and her current problems are alternated throughout the tale. Susannah's journey showcases a duel between artistic passion and family responsibilities, shedding light on the conflict that arises when one pursues their creative aspirations while meeting their parental duties. She had to put her singing career on hold so she could become a mother, and now she has to figure out how to balance what she wants while being a wife and a mother.

The scope for further studies includes, research through the lens of "Identity and Adoption", "Gender, Family and Sacrifice" and "Illness and the Body in Artistic Lives". As Susannah's life experience as an adoptee is deeply engrained in the novel, there are various instances where she questions her identity and belonging. It also affects her profession due to genetical health issues. Second area of research is family and sacrifice. The novel explores the protagonist's sacrifice as a wife and mother. She gives up her career in order to look after her son and when she tries to follow her passion in the later stage, her family is not supportive too. Another area of possible research is health studies. The novel showcases the struggles faced by Susannah due to her ailment, passed down to her through her birth mother's genes. It also includes various diagnosis related to Dupuytren's contracture with its pros and cons. Thus, these are some areas of further scope for research.

CONCLUSION

To conclude, Barbara Probst's *The Sound Between the Notes* has drawn acclaim for its musically based examination of identity, selflessness and the need for belonging. The journey turns into a process of self-realization, rekindling of her love for music. Probst's novel explores intricate familial relationships, thereby providing Susannah's character and her issues alongside rejection and identity more nuance. With every aspect considered, *The Sound Between the Notes* is an effective reminder of how important it is to follow one's passions while managing bonds and life's obstacles. Because *The Sound Between the Notes* examines the complications of identity, especially for women juggling personal aspirations with household responsibilities, it is incredibly pertinent to today's society. The difficulties many people encounter in following their passions while balancing social expectations are reflected through Susannah's journey. Probst's story emphasizes the value of self-discovery and the influence of past events on present decisions in a time when discussions about mental health, self-identity, and pursuing ambitions are becoming more and more common.

REFERENCES

1. Born, G. (2016). After relational aesthetics: Improvised musics, the social, and (re)theorising the aesthetic. *Improvisation and Social Aesthetics*, 5.
2. Epstein, H. (2000). *Melting The Venusberg: A Feminist Theology of Music*. McGill University, 5.
3. Ingleton, H. (2014). *Feminist Process in Sound Arts and Experimental Musics*. City University, 15.
4. Korsmeyer, C, and Weiser. (2021). "Feminist Aesthetics." *Stanford Encyclopedia of Philosophy*, Stanford University, plato.stanford.edu/entries/feminism-aesthetics/.
5. Mayhew, E. (1999). Women in Popular Music and the Construction of Authenticity. *Journal of Interdisciplinary Gender Studies*, 1.
6. McClary, S. (1990). Towards a Feminist Criticism of Music. *Revue de musique des universités canadiennes*.
7. Orita, H. M. (2024). *The Emergence, Circulation, and Influence of Turn-of-Millennium Feminist Music for Girl Audiences in the United States*. Chapel Hill.
8. Probst, B. (2021). *The Sound Between the Notes: A Novel*. She Writes Press.
9. Schiller, M. (2017). Resilience & Melancholy. *Pop Music, Feminism, Neoliberalism*, 1-5.
10. Wald, G. (1998). Just a Girl? Rock Music, Feminism, and the Cultural Construction of Female Youth. *Feminisms and Youth Cultures*, 25.
11. Weaver, M. (1993). Toward a Feminist Critical Perspective in Music History. *Circles: Buffalo Women's Journal of Law and Social Policy*, 35.